

Stable Neutrosophic Crisp Open Modulo Stable Neutrosophic Crisp Nowhere Dense Sets

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Abstract: Using the symmetric difference between the neutrosophic crisp set (NC–set) and stable Neutrosophic crisp open set (SNCO–set). It represents the complement of the quotient of the NC–set, SNCO–set, vice versa and linking with the family of stable Neutrosophic crisp (SNC) nowhere dense sets. They given the important properties of this concepts, we used it to build the stable Neutrosophic crisp open modulo SNC-nowhere dense sets. The results expiated amazing mathematical effects. This is what we have presented in this paper.

Keywords: Neutrosophic crisp sets, SNC– nowhere dense sets, SNCT–space, SNC – boundary set.

1. Introduction

The study is with in the neutrosophic crisp (NC-sets) path conditional on $Y^N = \langle Y_1, Y_2, Y_3 \rangle$ where $Y_i \cap Y_j = \emptyset, \forall i \neq j$. We also defined the type of intersection, union, complement, partial relations, and points in neutrosophic crisp sets was known by Salame [6,7] as more than one type under certain conditions. Therefore, in the case of studing any concept, we must determent those relations as well as the type of topology that we are working on, whence we take the stable neutrosophic crisp topological space (SNCT – space) [8]. The collection τ_X^N of NC – sets satisfies, $\phi_3^N, X_1^N \in \tau_X^N$ if $L^N, K^N \in \tau_X^N \exists H^N \in \tau_X^N \ni H^N \subseteq_1 L^N \cap_2 K^N$ and \forall index $\lambda, K_\lambda^N \in \tau_X^N \exists H^N \in \tau_X^N \ni H^N \subseteq_1 \cup_{2, \lambda \in \Lambda} K_\lambda^N$. Whence for any $L^N \in \tau_X^N$ is said to be SNCO – set and it is complement is SNCC – set. It is worth noting that we would like to point out that there are those who have set a synonymous definition for neutrosophic crisp set [2], as follows $\langle Y_1, \dots, Y_n, B_1, \dots, B_n, C_1, \dots, C_n \rangle$. There are many varied instruction's for these sets. For examples, you can see [1,5].

2. Operation Neutrosophic Crisp Set Theory

The operation on which our concepts are based on ;

- The union $\langle Y_1, Y_2, Y_3 \rangle \cup_2 \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle = \langle Y_1 \cup A_1, Y_2 \cap A_2, Y_3 \cap A_3 \rangle$.
- The intersection $\langle Y_1, Y_2, Y_3 \rangle \cap_2 \langle A_1, A_2, A_3 \rangle = \langle Y_1 \cap A_1, Y_2 \cup A_2, Y_3 \cup A_3 \rangle$.
- $A^N \subseteq Y^N$ iff $A_1 \subseteq Y_1, A_2 \subseteq Y_2, \text{ and } Y_3 \subseteq A_3$.
- The complement $(Y^N)^c = \langle Y_1^c, Y_2^c, Y_3^c \rangle$.

- The empty set $\emptyset^N = \langle \phi, X, X \rangle$.
- The universal set $X^N = \langle X, \phi, \phi \rangle$.
- The NC – points are :
 - $P^{N1} = \langle \{P\}, \phi, \{P\}^c \rangle \in_1 K^N$ iff $p \in K_1, P \notin K_3$.
 - $P^{N2} = \langle \phi, \{P\}, \{P\}^c \rangle \in_2 K^N$ iff $p \in K_2, P \notin K_3$.
 - $P^{N3} = \langle \{P\}, \phi, \phi \rangle \in_3 K^N$ iff $p \in K_1$.
 - $P^{N4} = \langle \phi, \{P\}, \phi \rangle \in_4 K^N$ iff $p \in K_2$.
- The SNC – interior and SNC – closure sets [8]
 - $Si(A^N) = \cup \{Y^N \in \tau_X^N; Y^N \subseteq A^N\}$,
 - $Scl(A^N) = \cap \{(Y^N)^c \in \tau_X^N; Y^N \subseteq F^N\}$.

It is noted that it is not necessary that the intersection of any two SNCO – sets is SNCO – set. Also the union of any collection of SNCD – sets is not necessary be SNCO – set.

The SNCT – space is called advance if it is closed under the intersection, and is called soon to arrive if it is closed under the union.

The quotient ; $A^N : Y^N = A^N \cup (Y^N)^c = [Y^N - A^N]^c$.

The symmetric difference ;

- $A^N \div Y^N = (A^N - Y^N) \cup (Y^N - A^N) = [(A^N : Y^N) \cap (Y^N : A^N)]^c$
- $A^N \div (J^N \div Y^N) = (A^N \cap J^N) \div Y^N$.
- $A^N \cap (J^N \div K^N) = (A^N \cap J^N) \div (A^N \cap K^N)$.
- $(A^N : Y^N) \cap Y^N = A^N \cap Y^N$.

3. SNC – Open Sets Modulo SNC – nowhere Dense Sets

The property of a set to be SNC-open modulo SNC-nowhere dense is also called the Baire property (in the large sense). We will reiew properties of this concept and the effect of neutrosophic crisp sets on it.

Definition 3 – 1 : Let (X^N, τ_X^N) be SNCT-space , then ;

- 1 – A^N is a SNC – boundary set if $Si(A^N) = \emptyset^N$.
 - $Scl((A^N)^c) = X^N$.
 - $Scl(A^N)$ is SNC – boundary iff $Scl(A^N) \subseteq Scl[Scl((A^N)^c)]$.
- 2 – A^N is a SNC – nowhere dense set if $Si(Scl(A^N)) = \emptyset^N$.
 - If $Scl(A^N)$ is SNC – boundary , then A^N is SNC – nowhere dense .

Proposition 3 – 2 : Let (X^N, τ_X^N) be advance SNCT – space. A^N is SNC – nowhere dense set iff $\exists Y^N \in \tau_X^N \setminus \{\phi^N\} \ni Y^N \cap A^N = \emptyset^N$.

Lemma 3 – 3 : The union of a SNC – boundary set and SNC – nowhere dense set is a SNC – boundary set.

Proposition 3 – 4 : If (X^N, τ_X^N) is a soon to arrive , then the union of two SNC – nowhere dense is a SNC – nowhere dense set .

Proof . Since τ_X^N is a soon to arrive ,whence $Scl(A^N)$ and $Scl(K^N)$ are SNCC – sets , and they are SNC – boundary ,if A^N and K^N are SNC – nowhere dense ,also By lemma3 – 3 the union

of them is SNC - boundary ,it follows that $A^N \cup K^N$ is SNC – nowhere dense set ,because $Scl(Scl(A^N)) = Scl(A^N)$. Similarly to K^N .

Remark 3 – 5:

- 1 - If Y^N is SNCO – set and SNCC – set , then $SNCFr(Y^N)$ is SNC – nowhere dense , where $SNCFr(Y^N) = Scl(Y^N) \cap Scl((Y^N)^c)$.
- 2 - If $Scl(Y^N) \cup (Y^N \cap Scl(K^N)) = \emptyset^N$, then $Scl(Y^N) \cap Scl(K^N)$ is a SNC - nowhere dense set .

Definition 3 – 6 :Let (X^N, τ_X^N) be a SNCT-space then ;

- NC – set $Y^N \subseteq K^N$ is a SNC – boundary set of K^N ,if $K^N \subseteq Scl(K^N - Y^N)$.
- NC – set $Y^N \subseteq K^N$ is a SNC – nowhere dense set of K^N , if $K^N \subseteq Scl[K^N - Scl(Y^N)]$.

Proposition 3 – 7. For any SNCT-space (X^N, τ_X^N) we have ;

- 1 -If Y^N is SNC – nowhere dense in $Scl(K^N)$, then $K^N \cap Y^N$ is SNC – nowhere dense in K^N .
- 2 – $Scl(K^N) - K^N$ is a SNC – boundary set in $Scl(K^N)$.
- 3 – $K^N \cap Si[SNCFr(K^N)]$ is a SNC – dense and SNC – boundary in $Si[SNCFr(K^N)]$.
- 4 - If Y^N is a SNC – boundary (SNC – nowhere dense) set in K^N , SO is Y^N relative to every set containing K^N .

Theorem 3 – 8 . Let (X^N, τ_X^N) be a SNCT-space .If A^N is a SNCO – set and K^N is SNC - boundary (SNC – nowhere dense) set , then SO is $A^N \cap K^N$ is a SNC – boundary set in A^N (SNC-nowhere dense set in $Scl(A^N)$) .

Proof. If K^N is a SNC - boundary ,then $K^N \subseteq Scl(A^N - K^N)$,whence $K^N \cap A^N \subseteq A^N \cap Scl[(K^N)^c] \subseteq Scl[A^N \cap (K^N \cap (A^N)^c)]$, and therefor $K^N \cap A^N$ is a SNC - boundary set in L^N . Similarly , if K^N is a SNC – nowhere dense set ,whence $K^N \cap A^N$ is a SNC - nowhere dense set in A^N . Also $K^N \cap A^N \subseteq Scl[A^N \cap (Scl(A^N \cap K^N))^c] \subseteq Scl[Scl(A^N) \cap (Scl(L^N \cap K^N))^c]$, and hence $A^N \cap K^N$ is a SNC – nowhere dense to $Scl(A^N)$, but $Scl(A^N) - A^N$ is a SNC – boundary set in $Scl(A^N)$, whence $K^N \cap Scl(A^N) \cap (A^N)^c$, is SNC – boundary set in $Scl(A^N)$. By proposition 3–4. $K^N \cap Scl(A^N) = (K^N \cap A^N) \cup (K^N \cap Scl(A^N) \cap (A^N)^c)$ is a SNC–nowhere dense set in $Scl(A^N)$.

Definition 3 – 9 . K^N is said SNC- open (closed) modulo SNC- nowhere dense if there is an SNCO- set (SNCC- set) $A^N \ni K^N - A^N$ and $A^N - K^N$ are SNC- nowhere dense (written $(K^N \sim A^N)$).

Example.

Take $Y = \{n, g, q\}$, $\tau_Y^N = \{\emptyset^N, Y^N, A^N, B^N, C^N\}$, where $A^N = \langle \{n\}, \{g\}, \{q\} \rangle$, $B^N = \langle \{n\}, \{g, q\}, \phi \rangle$ and $C^N = \langle \phi, \phi, \{q\} \rangle$, then $K^N = \langle \phi, \{n, g\}, \{q\} \rangle$ is SNC- open modulo SNC- nowhere dense to A^N , because $K^N - A^N$ and $A^N - K^N$ are SNC- nowhere dense sets.

Remark 3 – 10 . Let (X^N, τ_X^N) be a SNCT-space ,the following propositions are easily proved:

- Each SNC- closed (SNC- open) set is SNC- open (SNC- closed) modulo SNC- nowhere dense.
- If $K^N \sim A^N$ and $K^N \sim B^N$, then $K^N \sim B^N$, where $K^N, A^N, B^N \in \tau_X^N$.
- Let $L_1^N, L_2^N, K_1^N, K_2^N \in \tau_X^N$ and $L_1^N \sim L_2^N$ and $K_1^N \sim K_2^N$, then

- 1- $(L_1^N \cup K_1^N) \sim (L_2^N \cup K_2^N)$,
- 2- $(L_1^N \cap K_1^N) \sim (L_2^N \cap K_2^N)$,
- 3- $L_1^N - K_1^N \sim (L_2^N - K_2^N)$,

- $K^N \sim A^N$ iff K^N is of the form $K^N = (A^N - P^N) \cup O^N$ where P^N, O^N are SNC – nowhere dense sets. For if $K^N \sim A^N$, put $P^N = A^N - K^N$ and $O^N = K^N - A^N$, whence $K^N = (A^N - P^N) \cup O^N$. Conversely, $K^N - A^N = [(A^N - P^N) \cup (O^N)^c] - A^N \subseteq O^N$ is SNC – nowhere dense set, also $A^N - K^N = A^N - [(A^N - P^N) \cup O^N]^c \subseteq P^N$ is a SNC- nowhere dense, therefor $K^N \sim A^N$.
- The family of all SNC – open set module is field, in other word if P^N and K^N are SNC –open sets modulo SNC- nowhere dense sets, then so are $P^N \cup K^N$, $P^N \cap K^N$, and $(P^N)^c$.

Proposition 3 – 11. P^N is SNC- open modulo SNC- nowhere dense iff there is an SNCO- set $O^N \subseteq P^N$ and $P^N - O^N$ is a SNC – nowhere dense set, where (X, τ_X^N) is advance SNCT – space.

Proof. Suppose that $P^N - K^N$ and $K^N - P^N$ are SNC – nowhere dense sets. Put $O^N = P^N \cap Si(K^N) \subseteq K^N$, whence $P^N - O^N = (P^N - K^N) \cup (P^N \cup [Si(P^N)]^c) = (P^N - K^N) \cup (K^N \cap P^N \cap Scl((P^N)^c)) \subseteq (P^N - K^N) \cup Scl(K^N - P^N)$ is a SNC – nowhere dense set. Conversely, let O^N be a SNCO – set $\exists O^N \subseteq P^N$ and $P^N - O^N$ is a SNC- nowhere dense and $O^N \subset P^N$, so $O^N - P^N = \emptyset^N$ is a SNC – nowhere dense set and therefor P^N is SNC – open modulo SNC – nowhere dense set.

Proposition 3 – 12. L^N is SNC- open modulo SNC- nowhere dense iff $SNCFr(P^N)$ is a SNC – nowhere dense set.

Proof. By Proposition 3 – 11 there is an SNCO- set $H^N \subseteq P^N$ and $(H^N)^c \cap P^N$ is a SNC – nowhere dense, put $U^N = (H^N)^c \cap P^N$, whence $P^N = H^N \cup U^N$, and therefor $SNCFr(P^N) = SNCFr(H^N) \cup SNCFr(U^N)$, and by Remark 3 – 5(1) $SNCFr(H^N)$ is a SNC- nowhere dense set also $SNCFr(U^N)$ is a SNC- nowhere dense, hence $SNCFr(P^N)$ is a SNC- nowhere dense set.

Conversely, $P^N = Si(P^N) \cup [P^N \cap SNCFr(P^N)]$. Put $H^N = Si(P^N)$, whence $P^N \cap (H^N)^c \subseteq SNCFr(P^N)$. It follows that P^N is SNC- open modulo SNC – nowhere dense.

Corollary 3-13. H^N is SNC- open modulo SNC- nowhere dense iff H^N is difference of a SNCC – set and SNC - nowhere dense set

4. Conclusions

There is a proven fact in Neutrosophic crisp set theory which is, if K^N is a NC-set, then is not necessarily $(K^N)^c$ is satisfy any condition of NC-set, for example $(\langle \{u\}, \emptyset, \{v, g\} \rangle)^c = \langle \{v, g\}, X, \{u\} \rangle$ is non—NC-set, with $X = \{u, v, g\}$. Therefore, NCC-sets are not necessarily NC-sets for any Neutrosophic crisp topological spaces. Then they should be treated with extreme caution because Neutrosophic crisp algebra operations are not necessarily valid on them. This is considered one on the strengths of the NC-sets, which summarizes the relationship between them and the non-NC-sets. which has provided them with broad horizons in all branches of mathematics.

So we choose to study the nowhere dense, boundary and open modulo sets on SNCT- spaces, that have the ability to handle it, because the union and intersection of any two SNCO-sets (SNCC-sets) does not have to be SNCO-set (SNCC-set). Also, each NCT-space is SNCT-space but the converse may be not.

This research has established a basic foundation for studying the concept of SNC-first category set (it is the union of a countable sequence of SNC-nowhere dense sets), as it is considered a future work. In addition to studying the concepts SNC-dense in itself, SNC-scattered sets and SNC-discrete sets. In addition to the concepts in [3,4]. We can also study other neutrosophic crisp topological concepts, especially those works discussed by papers in [9-13] on stable neutrosophic crisp topological spaces which have further extended and details.

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